

The impact of information watch on strategic analytic behavior: the mediating role of knowledge sharing

L'impact de la veille de l'information sur le comportement stratégique analyseur : rôle médiateur du partage des connaissances

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Abstract

Information watch and its impact on strategic analytic behavior remain insufficiently explored as a combined phenomenon. This study aims to deepen the understanding of this relationship by analyzing the mediating role of knowledge sharing. A survey was conducted among 256 Tunisian high-tech companies. The results indicate that information watch, on its own, does not have a direct effect on strategic analytic behavior, but exerts a significant indirect influence through knowledge sharing. These findings enhance the theoretical understanding of the interplay between these concepts and provide practical recommendations for managers, particularly highlighting the importance of fostering a culture of sharing to strengthen the organization's strategic capabilities.

Keywords: Information watch; Knowledge sharing; Strategic behavior; Strategic analysis; High-tech companies.

Résumé

La veille de l'information et son impact sur le comportement stratégique analyseur sont encore peu explorés conjointement. Cette étude vise à mieux comprendre cette relation et à analyser le rôle médiateur du partage des connaissances. Une enquête a été menée auprès de 256 entreprises tunisiennes de haute technologie. Les résultats révèlent que la veille informationnelle, à elle seule, n'a pas d'effet direct sur le comportement stratégique d'analyse, mais qu'elle exerce une influence indirecte significative via le partage des connaissances. Ces résultats enrichissent la compréhension théorique des interactions entre ces concepts et offrent des recommandations concrètes aux dirigeants, notamment sur l'importance de promouvoir une culture de partage pour renforcer la capacité stratégique des organisations.

Mots-clés : Veille de l'information ; Partage des connaissances ; Comportement stratégique ; Analyse stratégique ; Entreprises de haute technologie

Introduction

In today's increasingly globalized world, business leaders face major challenges. They face fierce international competition in open markets, which requires them to implement specific measures and practices. According to previous research, adopting strategic behavior is paramount to managing risks and making decisions in situations of uncertainty (Fischer, et al., 2020, Sabherwal, et al., 2015, Madanoglu, 2011). Indeed, it enables the organization's objectives to be achieved while determining the best means of achieving them (Wang, et al., 2020). Among the various forms of strategic analytic behavior strategic behavior appears particularly appropriate (Fuertes, et al., 2020). Companies adopting this type of behavior are generally proactive, constantly seeking to keep abreast of the latest market trends and developments. They are often involved in in-depth research and studies to understand customer expectations, forecast changes in the industry and anticipate their competitors' moves.

This study focuses on high-tech companies. For these companies, adopting strategic analytic behavior enables their managers to discover new products and opportunities in the marketplace (Chatterjee, et al., 2022). To achieve this, some researchers (Olan, et al., 2019; Singh, 2020) believe it is often necessary to review the organizational structure in order to adapt to a constantly changing environment. In addition, Bizaguet (1991) points out that one of the administrative challenges facing these companies is to ensure effective coordination between different activities and foster innovation. Similarly, for other theorists, a possible solution to this problem lies in implementing appropriate information-gathering and knowledge-sharing techniques (Wang, 2020). It is therefore crucial for these companies to integrate analytic and collaborative approaches in order to remain competitive in their field.

What's more, according to several researchers (Manesh, 2020; Gorla, 2023), adopting an analyzer posture is tantamount to adopting strategic behavior in technological environments, relying on effective informational watch. In a context where information has become a key resource, the practice of information watch is essential for companies wishing to maintain their competitiveness. The ability to anticipate market trends and make informed strategic decisions is now a crucial challenge in ensuring the survival and growth of organizations.

However, information watch is more than just data collection, it also relies on good human resource management practices (Chen & Huang, 2009; Lin, 2011), a well-defined corporate culture (Don & Guadamillas, 2010; Nguyen & Mohamed, 2011) and a reorganization of organizational structures (Gold, Malhotra & Segars, 2001; Singh & Kant, 2009) to optimize the practice of watch. Furthermore, knowledge sharing plays a fundamental role, with leaders having a major influence on the direction and effectiveness of information watch practice within their organization (Rajiv & Yolande, 2001; Oesterreich, et al., 2022). Similarly, in-depth analysis of this information enables the identification of emerging trends, opportunities and potential threats. This is where the mediating role of knowledge sharing comes in. Indeed, knowledge sharing within an organization enables the information gathered during the watch to be disseminated and enriched, thus fostering a better understanding of the issues and problems that can have an impact on the company's strategic behavior. This practice also fosters a culture of collaboration and exchange between the various stakeholders, encouraging innovation and adaptability in the face of change.

In this context, a central question arises: to what extent does information watch influence strategic analytic behavior through the mediating role of knowledge sharing? To address this question, a quantitative study was conducted among 256 Tunisian high-tech companies, using a structured questionnaire and multivariate statistical analysis.

Thus, taking into account the theoretical observation that there is little research on the relationship between information watch and the strategic analytic behavior, this study aims to fill this gap and shed new light on the mediating role of knowledge sharing.

The findings also offer practical recommendations for business leaders. It is essential that they promote a culture of knowledge sharing within their teams, while integrating information watch as a strategic tool in the decision-making process. This approach will not only enhance the ability to anticipate market trends, but also improve the responsiveness and strategic agility of organizations in the face of a rapidly changing environment. In addition, encouraging inter-departmental collaboration and guaranteeing a fluid flow of information within the company will contribute to better strategic alignment, promoting more informed decision-making and enhanced competitiveness.

This article is structured as follows: after a review of the literature and the development of the theoretical framework, the adopted methodology is presented. The results of the empirical analysis are then reported, followed by a discussion of the managerial implications and avenues for future research.

1. Theoretical Framework

The aim of this part of the study is to present information watch, strategic analytic behavior and knowledge sharing, while analyzing the nature of the relationships that exist between these concepts.

To begin with, it is essential to recall the fundamental concepts underlying this research. The focus is on aspects related to strategic analytic behavior, knowledge sharing and watch practice.

Various studies have been carried out on strategic analytic behavior. Miles and Snow's (1978) typology is considered the most widely used. In this typology, Miles and Snow included several elements such as organizational strategies, structures and process variables, making it a rich and diverse typology. According to (Cancellier, et al., 2014), organizations with strategic analytic behaviour are both more innovative in their environment and more attentive and selective. By diversifying their business areas, these companies need to implement multiple planning processes and a strictly formalized assessment of new products or market opportunities. According to (Fuertes, et al., 2020), analyzers fall somewhere between prospectors and defenders. The foundations of Miles and Snow's theory indicate that if strategies are implemented properly, they will lead to significant gains in performance. This means that companies that adopt these strategies will see significant improvements in their results. Strategic business behavior analysis is a crucial approach for all companies seeking to remain competitive in the marketplace. By understanding the competitive environment, identifying opportunities and threats, and assessing internal resources and capabilities, a company can make informed strategic decisions that will enable it to prosper and differentiate itself from its competitors. According to (Fischer, et al., 2020), companies that adopt strategic analytic behavior face commercial challenges in maintaining market share, and seek to find new opportunities for their products. Their operational challenge is to maintain the effectiveness of their products and services, while remaining flexible enough to engage in

new activities. From an administrative point of view, it's a question of finding the right balance to manage these two aspects simultaneously. In this way, organizations can guarantee their success in the marketplace and ensure their growth.

On the other hand, strategic analytic behavior enables the company to understand and analyze its competitive environment in order to make appropriate strategic decisions. It is an essential process in the management of a company, helping to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that can influence the company's performance and competitive position.

As for information watch, this is a continuous monitoring of the company's environment, aimed at proactively gathering and searching for relevant information based on weak signals identified in this environment (Otmani, 2023). The practice of corporate information watch is an essential concept for ensuring a company's viability and competitiveness in a constantly changing economic environment. (Bouroubi, et al., 2023) assert that it consists in collecting, analyzing and disseminating relevant information on the market, competition, technological innovations, market trends, regulations and policies, and other aspects related to the company's activity.

Researchers such as (Ansoff, 1975), (Baumard, 1991) and (Chartrand, 2003) have introduced the notion of strategic watch, which consists of an informational process whereby a company looks to the future to listen to its environment, with the aim of creating new opportunities and reducing uncertainty. Moreover, (Jakobiak, 1999) argues that watch activities support strategic decision-making, monitor and track competitors, and support strategy planning and implementation. However, when it comes to the practical implementation of watch within an organization, several researchers stress the need to differentiate between different forms of watch.

(Goria, 2023) points out that through the proper practice of watch, companies can make informed decisions, anticipate market trends and developments, avoid potential risks and identify new opportunities for growth. This is why it is important to implement a structured and systematic information watch process to ensure that the company remains up-to-date and thrives in its industry. The practice of watch is not passive and is linked to the company's strategy.

2.2 Analysis of the Relationships Between the Study Variables

2.2.1 The effect of information watch on strategic analytic behavior

(Goria's, 2023) study of the effect of watch practice on strategic analytic behavior shows that watch practice amplifies individuals' attention and curiosity. Watch practitioners, constantly exposed to new information and updates in their field of specialization, develop a heightened interest in exploring and analyzing it in depth. As a result, this can involve more strategic analytic behavior, where they seek to understand the ongoing evolution of competitors. However, the results obtained by (Oesterreich, et al., 2022) demonstrate that the relationship between the practice of watch and strategic analytic behavior is indirect. They show that watch practice often involves the active gathering and synthesis of information from different sources. This requires real skills management to sort and organize the data obtained effectively. What's more, when companies apply these skills in their day-to-day practice, they are more inclined to adopt strategic analytic behavior when faced with environmental challenges.

This dynamic is also supported by (Kahneman's, et al., 1979) theory of selective attention, which postulates that individuals and organizations, faced with information overload, must be able to filter and process that which is most relevant to strategic decision-making. In the context of information watch, this theory suggests that the selective attention of managers or strategic analysts enables them to focus on essential information, thus fostering more strategic analytic behavior. In this sense, information watch plays a key role in activating the cognitive processes involved in strategic decision-making. This analytical process becomes all the more crucial in complex and changing business environments, where the ability to quickly grasp and interpret strategic information is crucial to organizational performance.

This dynamic is in line with the work of (Gmira&Khaouja, 2021), who highlight the central role of knowledge management and strategic intelligence as key levers for enhancing organizational performance, particularly in environments characterized by complexity and uncertainty. Their study underscores the importance of effectively structuring information flows to strengthen the quality of strategic decision-making.

Similarly, the results of (Rajiv & Yolande's, 2001) study ensure that the practice watch can lead to information overload and a decline in the ability to analyze in depth, which can reduce the propensity to adopt strategic analytic behavior. On the other hand, the practice of monitoring uses decision-support tools that can mitigate these negative effects. These include the search for new markets, the choice between two different development options, and the reconstitution of a company's strategic analytic behavior. Moreover, the aim of the study by (Stefanikova, et al., 2015) was to demonstrate the positive effect of watch practice on strategic analytic behavior through an empirical study conducted in Slovak companies in 2014. The results obtained proved that well-designed information watch can help companies in the strategic planning process by determining the intent and capability of its competitors, as well as the extent of the risks to which the company may be exposed. However, this requires the company to have a knowledge management process capable of meeting strategic needs and providing it with a dynamic view of the environment. Indeed, previous research has demonstrated a contradiction in the analysis of the relationship between watch practice and strategic analytic behavior. In this context, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1.Information watch practice has a positive and significant effect on strategic analytic behavior

2.2.2 The effect of information watch on knowledge sharing

With regard to the effect of watch practice on knowledge sharing, several authors emphasize the importance of the relationship between watch and knowledge sharing (Ganguly, 2019; Manesh, 2020; Bowie, 2022). They implicitly believe that this relationship contributes to improving business performance and competitiveness. This belief is studied empirically in the research work of Sahoo, et al., (2023), where they demonstrate that the practice of watch has a significant effect on knowledge sharing in companies. Watch information provides relevant, up-to-date information on market trends, technological innovations and competitors. This information is then shared within the organization, promoting the dissemination of knowledge and improving decision-making.

In this dynamic, knowledge management theory, and in particular Nonaka and Takeuchi's SECI model (1995), offers an important theoretical perspective for understanding the impact of information watch on knowledge sharing. According to this model, knowledge creation and

sharing in an organization takes place through four key processes: socialization, externalization, combination and internalization. Information watch plays a key role in the socialization and externalization phases, where tacit, often unstructured, information from the watch is shared within the organization through informal discussions, meetings or collaborative platforms. This information is then transformed into explicit, documented and systematized knowledge, and can be integrated into decision-making processes. In this way, watch facilitates the dissemination and management of knowledge by enabling the fluid circulation of information and enriching collective knowledge within the company, thereby strengthening strategic decision-making and improving organizational performance.

The study by (Olan, et al., 2022) also showed that companies that practice watch perform better and are more innovative than those that do not. By being constantly on the lookout for new information and developments, companies can anticipate market changes and react more quickly. This enables them to remain competitive and maintain their competitive edge. What's more, the practice of monitoring also promotes knowledge sharing within the company. Watchers gain valuable knowledge by collecting and analyzing relevant information, which they can then share with their colleagues. This dissemination of knowledge improves work processes, stimulates innovation and optimizes company performance.

However, the results of the study by (Fenni, et al., 2019) demonstrated that watch practice alone cannot guarantee knowledge sharing in companies. On the other hand, a proper business intelligence process, which starts with intelligence, goes through protection and ends with influence, optimizes knowledge sharing and stimulates collaboration between the various players. Other research reinforces this relationship between watch information and knowledge sharing. The work of (Lee & Choi, 2018) shows that strategic watch not only improves knowledge management, but also collaboration between different departments within a company. They point out that information derived from watch helps to reduce organizational silos by promoting the fluid flow of information and improving internal communication. What's more, a study by (Zhang, et al., 2017) demonstrated that information watch helps create an environment conducive to innovation, as it facilitates the exchange of knowledge between employees, leading to more creative solutions tailored to market challenges.

The second hypothesis is as follows: **H2**. Watch practice has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing.

2.2.3. The effect of knowledge sharing on strategic analytic behavior

As for the effect of knowledge sharing on strategic analytic behavior, the results of a study by (Singh, et al., 2021) stated that close knowledge exchange within companies positively influences strategic analytic behavior. The authors explain that this enables them to identify opportunities and risks more easily and make more informed decisions. (Wang, et al., 2020) came to a similar conclusion. They showed that knowledge sharing fosters innovation and creativity. By offering employees new ideas and fostering collaboration, companies can stimulate the generation of new ideas and encourage the emergence of innovative solutions. This can lead to increased competitiveness in the marketplace. Sharing knowledge also helps to reinforce a learning culture within a company.

To complete this analysis and strengthen the argument, it is pertinent to refer to knowledge management theory, in particular the organizational learning model (Argyris & Schön, 1978), which explores how knowledge sharing influences strategic corporate behavior, including the strategic analytic behaviour.

According to this theory, organizational learning is based on an organization's ability to accumulate and share knowledge, enabling its members to adapt and respond effectively to changes in the environment. In the context of analyzer-like strategic behavior, organizations that foster a knowledge-sharing culture enable their employees to analyze market trends, risks and opportunities more effectively. This continuous learning process facilitates strategic decision-making based on up-to-date, relevant information.

The study by (Kogut & Zander, 1992) shows that knowledge sharing directly promotes organizations' strategic behaviors, particularly in terms of decision-making and adaptation to market changes. They point out that the circulation of strategic information throughout the organization enables decision-makers to better anticipate market trends and rapidly adjust strategies.

Furthermore, the work of (Gupta & Govindarajan, 2000) revealed that companies that implement effective knowledge-sharing mechanisms, such as shared databases and collaborative processes, directly improve their ability to adopt strategic analytic behavior geared towards innovation and anticipation of market needs. These studies suggest that when

strategic information is shared seamlessly across the organization, it facilitates relevant strategic decision-making and strengthens the company's competitiveness.

As a result, knowledge sharing can have a positive impact on strategic analytic behaviour within the company. However, based on the structure of previous studies, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H3. Knowledge sharing has a significant positive impact on strategic analytic behavior

2.2.4. The mediating effect of knowledge sharing in the relationship between information watch and strategic analytic behavior

For the mediating effect of knowledge sharing in the relationship between watch practice and strategic analytic behavior, strategy scholars have focused on the various variables that are apt to affect strategic corporate behaviors (Wieder & Ossimitz, 2015; Sundiman, 2018; Mat Noor, et al., 2021), Chaudhuri, et al., 2022). Insights from these studies can enhance our understanding of the relationship between information watch practice and strategic analytic behavior, and offer practical explanations for the role of knowledge sharing in this relationship. (Wang, et al., 2022) demonstrated a positive relationship between information watch practice and knowledge sharing. They asserted that knowledge sharing plays an essential role in the relationship between watch practice and strategic analytic behavior in companies. By facilitating the dissemination of and access to information. While (Chen&Huang, 2015) in their study used regression analysis to test the hypotheses for a sample of 146 companies. They confirmed that the relationship between watch practice and knowledge sharing is indirect, and that better human resource management improves the relationship between the two.

As for (Sulistiawan, et al., 2022), they suggested a positive relationship between strategic analytic behavior and knowledge sharing via competency management. The results of their study show that knowledge sharing can enrich understanding of strategic issues, develop new skills and perspectives, and assist companies in decision-making. Knowledge sharing also fosters collaboration and cooperation between members of the organization, strengthening the company's ability to make effective strategic decisions.

In view of these findings, the practice watch is likely to affect the strategic analytic behavior via knowledge sharing, although no study has proven the mediating possibility of knowledge sharing to our knowledge. Accordingly, the present study formulates the following hypothesis:

H4: Knowledge sharing plays a mediating role in the relationship between watch practice and strategic analytic behavior.

In fact, the conceptual model below summarizes the statement of the problem studied and denotes the hypotheses put forward. (figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Source : Authors

3. Research methodology

First, the sample selection and survey procedure will be presented. Next, the measurement of variables will be discussed.

3.1. Sample selection and survey procedure

A questionnaire was created and sent to a sample of 295 managers from Tunisian companies operating in the high-tech sector. 256 questionnaires were received, representing a response rate of 86.7%. The characteristics of the sample are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Age

	Number	Percentage	Percentage valid	Percentage Cumulative
To 20 à 30 years	136	50,7	49,8	39,9
To 31 à 40 years	95	39,9	39,6	60,1
Over de 41 years	25	9,4	10,6	100,0
Valid Total	256	100,0	100,0	

Source : Authors

Table2 : Type

	Number	Percentage	Percentage valid	PercentageCumulative
Male	142	55,4	55,4	67,9
Valid Female	114	44,6	44,6	100,0
Total	256	100,0	100,0	

Source : Authors

This non-probability sampling method does not guarantee sample representativeness, unlike random sampling, even though it is based on a reasoned choice of individuals from the population. The choice of this method was motivated by its simplicity and speed in selecting sampling units (Johnston, et al., 2010). The survey lasted eight months, from January to August 2023. Because of its dynamic and innovative nature, the high-tech sector was specifically chosen. From this perspective, it offers a stimulating framework for studying the impact of information intelligence on the strategic analytic behavior, and the importance of knowledge sharing as a mediator.

3.2. Measurement of variables

The “ strategic analytic behavior ” variable refers to the scale used by (Avci, et al., 2011) in their study of (Miles &Snow's, 1978) strategic archetypes. This multi-item scale, which operationalizes (Miles &Snow's, 1978) strategic analytic behavior, has been proposed and field-tested in several research studies (Meye, et al., 1990; Croteau, 2001, Madanoglu, 2011, Sabherwal, et al., 2015, Lecocq, 2004). It is regarded as an effective tool with great potential for management and research. It should be remembered that this approach, considered the

most widely recognized, is also seen as the most comprehensive conceptualization of strategic organizational behavior, as (Batac, et al., 2019) also point out. In this research, a Likert scale used comprising 9 items to measure “ strategic analytic behavior ”. Participants were asked to indicate their degree of agreement or disagreement with each item. The 7 items selected were chosen to assess the extent to which respondents agreed or disagreed with the proposals. An example of a selected item is: “In our company, all levels of management contribute to strategic decision-making and the preparation of strategic plans”. Cronbach's alpha for this scale is 0.918.

In order to measure the “information watch” variable, this study refers to the measurement scale used by (Degan, et al., 2018). This scale is based on the work of watch researchers such as (Phanuel & Levy, 2003), (Bournois & Romani, 2000), Levet,2001) as well as practitioners such as (Jakobiak,1998), (Bloch,1995), (Hassid & Moinet,1997), (Martinet & Marti,1995). The Likert scale used ranged from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”. Three items were selected to measure the “watch” variable (e.g.: “The plurality of information sources is an asset for companies”). With a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.875.

Concerning the “knowledge sharing” variable, with reference to the measurement scale of Donate, et al., (2014), this variable is evaluated on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to (strongly agree). Among the 6 items selected, for example: “There are regular meetings at which our employees are informed of new initiatives”. Cronbach's alpha for this scale is 0.812.

4. Results

First, the results of the exploratory analysis will be presented (3.1.), followed by those of the confirmatory analysis (3.2.).

4.1. Results of exploratory analysis

First, the results of the exploratory analysis will be presented (3.1.), followed by those of the confirmatory analysis (3.2.).

Table 3: Results of exploratory analysis

Dimensions	KMO and Bartlett Test	Selected items and QR		VP	α
Strategic analytic behavior	Test de Bartlett = 0.000 KMO = 0,946	Analy2=0,842		1.798	0,918
		Analy3=0,854			
		Analy4=0,785			
		Analy5=0,735			
		Analy6=0,789			
		Analy7=0,775			
Information watch	KMO = 0,822 Test de Bartlett = 0.000	watch.1	0,879	1.045	0,875
		watch.2	0,854		
		watch.3	0,898		
Knowledge sharing	KMO = 0,785 Test de Bartlett = 0.000	Partag.1	0,864	1.008	0,812
		Partag.3	0,832		
		Partag.4	0,856		
		Partag.6	0,985		
		Partag.7	0,878		
		Partag.8	0,775		

Note: RQ: Representation Quality, EV: Eigenvalues, α : Cronbach's Alpha

Source : Authors

The KMO values for the three study variables indicate that the items are suitable for factor analysis (coefficients greater than 0.7). In addition, it is emphasized that the data can be factorized. It is also important to note that the quality of the representation of the various items is higher than 0.5. The eigenvalues for each variable are all well above 1 (1.798 for strategic analytic behavior, 1.049 for information watch and 1.008 for knowledge sharing). In addition, Cronbach's alpha for each variable exceeds the critical threshold of 0.7 (0.918 for strategic analytic behavior, 0.875 for information watch and 0.812 for knowledge sharing). These results indicate a satisfactory internal consistency of the measurement scale used for the three study variables.

4.2. Validation of dimensions obtained in confirmatory analyses

AMOS 22 software, based on the method of (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), is used in the confirmatory analysis, which validates the measures. The Hayes method is used to study the mediating role of knowledge sharing at the level of the model to be tested, and structural analysis was used to test the significance of causal links using the maximum likelihood (ML) method. Initially, first-order factors are considered to be strongly linked, as the Jöreskog ratio reaches 0.7. A convergent validity ratio greater than or equal to 0.5 justifies verification of convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The results are in line with these recommendations. In addition, discriminant validity was verified when the square root of the mean variance extracted was less than the correlations between the latent variables in the model (Fornell and Larcker 1981). Thus, the reliability and validity of the measures are presented in the table below.

Table4: Results of confirmatory analyses

Dimensions	Reliability (Jöreskog's Rhô)	Convergent validity (AVE)	Discriminant validity
Watch	0.935	0,765	0,889
Sharing	0.907	0,708	0.922
Strategic analytic behavior	0.946	0.712	0.944

Source : Authors

4.3. Presentation of the structural model and hypothesis testing

Structural analysis is used in this study to assess the goodness of fit of the proposed model and to test the causal links between our baseline variables. Based on the results in Table 5, the goodness-of-fit indices are satisfactory, given the empirical acceptance thresholds.

Table5: Structural model fit (ML estimation)

Indexes	From Parsimony	Absolute				Incremental	
	Chi-deux/ddl	GFI	AGFI	RMR	RMSEA	NFI	CFI
Values	2,224	0,976	0,885	0,046	0,068	0,889	0,948

Source : Authors

The following table presents the results of our confirmatory analysis, as well as the acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses formulated in our research study.

Table6: Results of structural model relationship analysis

Measurement Model Relationships	Results	Hypothesis
Information watch→ strategic analytic behavior	t=1,455<1,96 ; p=0,143>0,05	Rejected
Information watch →Knowledge sharing	(t=4,089>1,96 ; p=0,000<0,05	Validated
Knowledge sharing → strategic analytic behavior	(t=4,564>1,96 ; p=0,000<0,05	Validated

Source : Authors

Table 6 presents the results of a measurement model analysis of the relationships between information watch, strategic analytic behavior and knowledge sharing. For the relationship between information watch and strategic analytic behavior ($t=1.455 < 1.96$ and $p=0.143 > 0.05$), hypothesis H1, which states that the practice of information watch has a positive and significant effect on strategic analytic behavior, is rejected. On the other hand, for the relationship between information watch and knowledge sharing, $t=4.089 > 1.96$ and $p=0.000 < 0.05$, hypothesis H2, which states that information watch has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, is validated. As for the relationship between knowledge sharing and strategic analytic behavior $t=4.564 > 1.96$ and $p=0.000 < 0.05$, subsequently, hypothesis H3 which states that knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on strategic analytic behavior.

The role of knowledge sharing as a mediator in the relationship between information watch and strategic analytic behavior was tested using the method of Preacher and Hayes. The process followed by the Preacher and Hayes method is as follows: regressions 1 and 3 of the Baron and Kenny model are run, followed by a bootstrap test ($n=5000$) to test for indirect effect. Significance criteria are shown in Table 7.

Table7: Significance criteria for the Preacher and Hayes method

Coefficient	Method	Criteria sig.	Effetsig.if
A	Régression	P-value	$p < 0,05$
B	Régression	P-value	$p < 0,05$
Coefficient	Régression	P-value	$p < 0,05$
a x b	Bootstrap	Confidence interval	$IC < 0 > IC$

Source : Authors

If all the values obtained meet these conditions, this means that the mediation hypothesis cannot be rejected. According to Zhao et al (2014) in a non-recursive three-variable causal model. There are three patterns that are compatible with mediation and two that are not: the complementary mediation pattern, where the mediated effect ($a \neq b$) and the direct effect (c) both exist and point in the same direction. The competitive mediation scheme, where the mediated effect ($a \neq b$) and the direct effect (c) both exist and point in opposite directions. The pattern of indirect mediation only, where the mediated effect ($a \neq b$) exists, but there is no direct effect; the pattern of direct non-mediation only, where the direct effect (c) exists, but there is no indirect effect; finally, the pattern of non-mediation without effect, where there is neither direct nor indirect effect.

In this research, watch practice had a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing ($a=0.76$; $t=16.7220$; $p=0.000$). Controlling for information watch, the effect of knowledge sharing on strategic analytic behavior was positive and significant ($b=0.4$; $t=6.5$; $p=0.000$). Furthermore, the total effect of information watch on strategic analytic behavior was significant ($c=0.35$; $t=4.84$; $p=0.000$). Finally, the indirect effect of information watch on scanner behavior was positive and significant ($a*b=0.08$), with a 95% confidence interval excluding 0 (from 0.08 to 0.38). These results therefore indicate complementary mediation (Zhao et al, 2010). Table 8 shows these results.

Table8: Preacher and Hayes test results

Output variable: Knowledge sharing				
	Coeff	SE	T	P
Constant	0.000	0,0492	0.0000	1.0000
information watch(a)	0,7664	0,0503	16.7220	0,0000
Output variable: Strategic analytic behavior				
	Coeff	SE	T	P
Constant	0.000	0.483	0.000	1.0000
information watch (b)	0.4756	0.0778	6.5246	0.0000
Knowledge sharing (c)	0.35685	0.0786	4.8456	0.0000
Direct eve effect on Strategic analytic behavior				
	Effet	SE	T	P
	0.4775	0.0793	6.5846	0.0000
Indirect effect on strategic behavior analyzer				
	Effet	BootSE	BootLCI	BootULCI
Knowledge sharing	0.2556	0.0806	0.0845	0.3877

Source : Authors

The tables present the results of this study, supporting hypothesis H4 that knowledge sharing mediates the relationship between information watch and strategic analytic behavior.

5. Discussion

The aim of this research is to study how the practice of information watch affects the strategic analytic behavior, taking into account knowledge sharing as a mediating variable. This approach makes it possible to test the four hypotheses formulated in this study (H1, H2, H3 and H4). Indeed, the empirical non-validation of H1, which suggests that the practice of information watch has a positive impact on strategic analytic behavior, contradicts (Goria's ,2023) recent findings in other contexts. However, our results converge with those of (Oesterreich, et al., 2022) and Rajiv & Yolande, 2001). Thus, strategic analytic behavior is not simply a matter of adhering to a watch practice within the company. This is due to the existence of intermediate variables such as human resources management, leadership, organizational structure and knowledge sharing, which influence the relationship between information watch and strategic analytic behavior.

The validation of H2, which maintains that the practice of information watch has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, confirms the previous findings of (Olan, et al.,

2022; Sahoo, et al., 2023). One possible interpretation of this validation is that the company cannot share its knowledge without implementing an appropriate information watch practice. Therefore, the main objective of an organization's use of information watch practice is to become aware of its knowledge, both individually and collectively (Alavi & Leidner, 2001).

Hypothesis H3, which states that knowledge sharing has a positive effect on strategic analytic behavior, is validated. Consequently, it is essential to foster a knowledge-sharing culture within organizations, to enable better decision-making based on reliable, up-to-date information. The work of (Wang, et al., 2020; Singh, et al., 2021) supports this idea, demonstrating a significant correlation between knowledge sharing and strategic analytic behavior. Thus, by promoting the circulation of knowledge within the company, individuals are better able to demonstrate rigor and precision in their analyses, which contributes to improving the performance of the organization as a whole.

It was confirmed that hypothesis H4, which holds that knowledge sharing plays a mediating role in the relationship between watch practice and strategic analytic behavior, is valid. This finding reinforces our belief that there is a complementary mediation provided by knowledge sharing. Indeed, this result is in line with the studies of many researchers, such as (Chen & Huang, 2015; Sulistiawan, et al., 2022; Chatterjee, et al., 2023) who assert that watch practice has no direct effect on strategic analytic behavior.

Consequently, frequent use of watch practice and improved knowledge dissemination can be seen as indicators of the adoption of strategic analytic behavior. These findings should attract the attention of managers of Tunisian high-tech companies, as they offer opportunities for action to adopt strategic analytic behavior.

6. Conclusion

This study aims to assess the role of knowledge sharing as a mediator in the relationship between watch practice and strategic analytic behavior. Although knowledge sharing has been shown in previous research to be correlated with watch practice and strategic analytic behavior (Goria, 2023; Ganguly, 2019; Singh, et al., 2021), no previous research has specifically investigated it as a mediating variable. Thus, this research provides empirical support by holding a conceptual model with key findings. Firstly, it significantly demonstrates

that knowledge sharing plays a mediating role in the relationship between information watch practice and the choice of strategic analytic behavior in high-tech companies. The results highlight the importance of promoting a knowledge-sharing culture within organizations, in order to foster more effective strategic decision-making geared towards fine-grained analysis of the competitive environment. It is therefore essential for company directors and managers to put in place mechanisms and policies designed to encourage knowledge sharing, and to enhance the value of the information gathered through the practice of intelligence gathering. By encouraging this collaboration and exchange of information, companies can optimize their competitive performance.

This result offers several contributions. It enhances managers' awareness of the importance of information watch in maintaining and strengthening their companies' competitiveness. It also enables them to structure information management and knowledge-sharing processes more efficiently by mobilizing appropriate organizational, human, and technological resources. Such structuring facilitates the successful implementation of intelligence activities, improves strategic orientation, and supports the international development of companies.

Nevertheless, it is worth highlighting certain limitations of this study that restrict the scope of the conclusions reached. Firstly, it is important to mention that the sample used for the quantitative analyses cannot guarantee statistical representativeness, despite considerable efforts to collect the data rigorously. In addition, this research opens up interesting avenues of investigation. Indeed, it would be relevant to consider adding a qualitative study using research methods such as interviews and/or observations. The use of these techniques would make it possible to explore certain tacit aspects of this research. Finally, future studies should also look at the mediation of other variables, such as the storage, transfer and application of knowledge.

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